

STUDENT PROGRAM MANAGEMENT IN IMPROVING SCHOOL STUDENT LEARNING ACHIEVEMENT MTA KARAWANG INTEGRATED ISLAMIC FOUNDATION

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Abstract

This research is based on facts that show problems in elementary school student management, there are still members of student organizations who lack discipline, lack of communication in carrying out student organization activities, there are student activity programs that have not been implemented, and there is a lack of student discipline development. Based on the background of this problem, it is necessary to carry out research related to "Student Management in Improving Primary School Student Achievement. This research aims to get an overview and analyze the planning, implementation and evaluation of student management programs in elementary schools. This research uses a qualitative approach with a case study method at the Majelis Tafsir Al-Quran Karawang Integrated Islamic Primary School. The theoretical basis used is the management of GR Terry. The results of the research show that the management aspect in the student program has been running in accordance with the rules of management theory, but the supporting resources in the student program are still not optimal, and this has implications for continuous improvement.

Keywords: Management, Student Affairs, Student Achievement.

I. INTRODUCTION

Republic of Indonesia Law Number 20 of 2003, concerning the National Education System and Government Regulation Number 19 of 2005, and further elaborated in Permendiknas Number 19 of 2007 that "every educational unit is obliged to meet the education management standards that apply nationally", several aspects of management standards What schools must fulfill includes: (1) program planning, (2) implementation of work plans, (3) monitoring and evaluation, (4) school/madrasah leadership, and (5) management information systems. Then Permendiknas Number: 39 of 2008, concerning Student Development Article 1 The aim of student development: a) Develop students' potential optimally and in an integrated manner which includes talent, interest and creativity; b). Strengthening students' personalities to realize school resilience as an educational environment so as to avoid negative efforts and influences that conflict with educational goals;

The management of student programs implemented by schools is directed at helping the development of students at school, through several methods, including extracurricular development. Student program management can assist in extracurricular development that is designed at the beginning of the year. This can help students develop their interests and talents outside academic subjects. The implications of the effectiveness of student management are to increase students' overall potential, namely thinking potential, emotional potential, physical potential and others.

Effective student management can also help in building a culture of student discipline in elementary schools. This helps students develop good attitudes and behavior, as well as increasing student independence. Thus, student management can aim at developing students in elementary schools through the various methods mentioned above.

School student activities related to student activities and regulated by student management. Every education officer within an educational institution will be involved in student activities.

School principals have an important role in improving organizational activities in the student affairs sector. The educational process is one of the most effective media for giving birth to a generation that has good morals and ethics. School student activities have an important role in student education and development. Student activities are regulated by student management and are a school priority program. Likewise, teachers as the party responsible for children's education at school are required to act skillfully and creatively so that children can increase their knowledge, namely teachers are required to provide time outside of official hours determined by the government which are often referred to as extracurricular activities.

Students are the main clients who must be served, therefore students must be involved actively and appropriately, not only in the teaching and learning process, but also in school activities. The success of student learning achievement cannot be separated from student management, which is the arrangement and arrangements related to students from entry to exit of students from school. This management is not only limited to recording student data but also covers a wider range of operational activities at school .

Facts that show problems in elementary school student management indicate that: 1) There are still members of school student organizations who are less united in carrying out student activities at school; 2) There are still members of student organizations who lack discipline in implementing; 3) Lack of communication in carrying out student organization activities, there are student activity programs that have not been implemented. Another problem in the context of student management is that teachers do not carry out regular attendance and the school does not record complete student data in the main book. Lack of student discipline training. Student services, especially the library section, are inadequate. In the management of educators, upgrading and scientific discussions are rarely held. Awards are rarely given to educators who excel and have good performance. Infrastructure management, such as incomplete library books, damaged and dirty bathroom buildings.

Aspects of Curriculum management, Teachers are unable to organize their time so that at the end of the semester, material is often compressed, Teachers rarely prepare Learning Plans before teaching. Management of educational administration, there are no administrative staff, so that management activities are carried out by teachers, management problems related to correspondence between schools are hampered

Based on this background description, it is necessary to carry out research related to "Student Affairs Management in Improving Elementary School Student Achievement. This research aims to get an overview and analyze the planning, implementation and evaluation of student management programs in elementary schools. This research uses a qualitative approach with a case study method. The theoretical basis used is the management of GR Terry.

II. THEORITICAL REVIEW

Student management is the management of activities related to students from the beginning of entry (even before entering) to the end (graduation) of an educational institution. education begins to create an atmosphere that is conducive to the ongoing effective teaching and learning process.

Student management in schools is the arrangement or management of activities related to students at school so that learning activities can run smoothly, orderly and orderly. According to Usman, H (2013: 178) that student management is the entire process of activities that are planned and carried out deliberately as well as ongoing guidance for all students so that they can participate in the teaching and learning process effectively and efficiently. Another opinion expressed by Mulyasa (2003:46) is that student management or student (student) management is one of the operational areas of School Based Management (MBS). Student management is the arrangement or regulation of activities related to students, from entry to exit of students from a school.

School

Student management is not only an activity programmed by the school, such as new student admissions, placement and student development, but it is also hoped that students' potential, both spiritual and physical, can develop optimally. (Hermawan, 2015:10).

The aim of student management is to organize all kinds of activities of students so that the activities carried out can support the learning process in educational institutions so that they can run as they should. Student programs in schools are based on several theoretical foundations, which can be explained as follows: 1) Student organizations are the process of managing all matters relating to students, school development starting from planning student admissions and coaching. Student management is basically a combination of two words, namely management and student affairs. Student management is to organize various activities in the field of student affairs so that learning activities in schools can run smoothly, in an orderly and orderly manner. In developing a

student management program, organizers must refer to the regulations in effect at the time the program was implemented.'

The basic concept of student management is an effort to regulate students and manage activities related to students at school in order to create a conducive learning atmosphere. Student management can help improve the quality of education in schools in several ways, including 1) helping to improve student discipline through organizing activities related to students at school. One example is holding scouting activities which can help students develop discipline and responsibility; 2) Increase student participation in school activities. By providing interesting and useful activities, students will be more interested in participating and being active in these activities. This can help increase students' motivation and enthusiasm for learning; 3) Improve coordination between students, teachers and parents; 4) helps improve coordination between students, teachers and parents. With good coordination, a conducive atmosphere will be created for the learning process at school. This can help improve the quality of education in schools; 5) Increasing the development of student potential, through organizing activities that can help students develop their talents and interests. By providing activities that suit students' talents and interests, students will be more motivated to develop their potential and achieve better achievements. Thus, student management can help improve the quality of education in schools through the various methods mentioned above.

III. RESEARCH METHODS

This research uses a qualitative approach, the research method used is a case study, which is a strategy that is more suitable for research where the main research question is concerned with how or why (Yin, 2013). The research location is the Majelis Tafsir Al-Quran Karawang Integrated Islamic Primary School. The research subjects were school principals, teachers, parents of students, and students. The research implementation schedule starts from May 2023 to August 2023. The data collected during the implementation of this research is in the form of qualitative data originating from the data collection process using triangulation techniques, namely observations, documentation studies and in-depth interviews. Data collection instruments are equipped with research grids, observation guides, documentation studies and interviews, the researcher himself as the main instrument is directly involved in extracting information. The research subjects were schools, principals, deputy principals and teachers. The criteria used to improve and determine the validity of data are the degree of trustworthiness, transferability, dependability and confirmability. Data validity testing was carried out using triangulation techniques and data source triangulation. Data analysis uses a qualitative model which includes data collection, data reduction and display, and drawing conclusions

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

General description of the research location, namely the Majelis Tafsir Al-Quran Integrated Islamic Elementary School Jl. Kalihurip, RT 006/ RW 002, Duren, Klari, Karawang, with accreditation status A. "School Vision" seeks to create graduates who have noble, intelligent and accomplished morals based on correct Islamic law and straight creeds.

The school's mission is to accustom children to have noble morals and straight creeds, to guide students to understand the correct Islamic law, to train students to recognize their own potential to optimize their intelligence, to carry out learning that is fun, effective, efficient, productive and competitive to foster achievement motivation, to train children to have the ability to read, write, memorize the Al-Quran correctly.

a. Student Program Planning

Based on the results of observations, in-depth interviews and documentation studies regarding student program planning at Integrated Islamic Primary Schools, starting with forming a discussion forum and making a study on the implementation of student management, as well as establishing a program plan, this is to formulate and develop programs in the student affairs sector so that learning activities The school can run smoothly, orderly and orderly. The student program is prepared by the principal together with the deputy head of student affairs. An important aspect in planning student programs begins with identifying student and school needs, through an analysis process of student and school needs, both in terms of academic, non-academic and character development. By understanding these needs, you can design student programs that are relevant and effective. Involving students, teachers, parents and other school parties in the student program planning process will help ensure that the programs prepared meet the needs and expectations of all parties in the school. Then use references to educational regulations and standards, this is to ensure that the student programs that are prepared comply with applicable educational regulations and standards. This will help maintain the quality and sustainability of the program. Next is adjustment to the school's vision, mission and goals. Student programs are aligned with the school's vision, mission and goals. This will help achieve the educational goals desired by the school.

One aspect of the student planning program at school is the New Student Admissions Program: This program includes the process of accepting new students at school, including selection and registration, then the Student Development Program: This program includes coaching students in various aspects, such as developing talents, interests, and student creativity, development of national and state attitudes, and increased physical fitness. Followed by the Extracurricular Development Program: This program includes coaching students in extracurricular activities, such as sports, arts and social activities

Academic and Non-Academic Excellence Program: This program includes coaching students in academic and non-academic fields, such as olympiads, competitions and activities that support student achievement.

Short-Term and Long-Term Work Program Planning: A short-term work program is a plan for achieving activity goals within a period of 1 semester to 1 year, while a long-term work program is a plan for achieving activity goals within a period of 2-5 years.

In preparing student program planning, it is carried out in deliberation with all elements in the school environment so that the work program that is realized is a joint program that will be realized well.

b. Implementation of Student Programs

Based on the results of observations, in-depth interviews and documentation studies at the Integrated Islamic Elementary School, it was carried out through the stages of implementing student programs related to student activities to develop their character and potential, through conditioning and habituation. This conditioning is carried out by implementing various school rules that favor the development of discipline, which is the task of the Deputy Principal for Student Affairs. Hi, this relates to the functions and responsibilities of the Deputy Principal for Student Affairs. Some of the activities carried out in student management to improve student achievement at school include: Planning for new student admissions: Planning for new student admissions is carried out with the aim of selecting students who are qualified and have the potential to develop at school. This can help improve the quality of student achievement in elementary schools. Data collection on student learning progress is carried out to determine the extent of students' abilities in understanding the subject matter. By knowing students' learning progress, teachers can provide more effective assistance and guidance to students

Arrangement of activities related to students. Arrangements for student-related activities are carried out to help students develop their potential and talents. Activities such as scouting, sports, arts, and so on can help students develop themselves and improve the quality of education at school. Student development is carried out to help students develop positive attitudes, such as discipline, responsibility, cooperation, and so on. This can help improve the quality of education in schools. Increased coordination between students, teachers and parents is carried out to create a conducive atmosphere in the learning process at school. With good coordination, a harmonious and mutually supportive atmosphere will be created between students, teachers and parents.

Developing student character development programs, such as developing devotion to God Almighty, national insight, student leadership, student entrepreneurship, talents and abilities, physical fitness and artistic abilities, fostering and implementing order, cleanliness, security, health, tidiness and friendliness. Organize and coordinate order, discipline and student attendance at school as well as problems related to this

Coordinating supervision programs for students who have problems in teaching, personal adjustment, social adjustment and emotional adjustment, coordinating the implementation of health and safety programs for students, coordinating and developing activity programs related to the activities of the National Education Service, organizing meetings between student representatives and teachers and employees, together with the Deputy Principal for Curriculum to develop a guidance program for exemplary or outstanding students, carry out academic orientation activities for new students and introduce a non-violent environment.

The implementation of student programs in schools involves many parties, such as the Deputy Principal for Student Affairs, teachers, employees and the students themselves. The student program aims to provide social skills training for students, such as communication, teamwork and leadership training. This can help students in developing their social skills, organizing extracurricular activities that can help students in developing

their social skills, such as arts activities, sports, and self-development social activities. Carrying out flag ceremonies and commemorating religious holidays can help students understand national and religious values. Guidance and Counselling: Guidance and counseling programs are implemented to help students overcome personal, social, and academic problems. These student activities can help students develop their potential, talents and interests outside normal class hours, as well as help new students adapt to the school environment. Apart from that, student activities can also help students develop social skills, leadership and responsibility.

c. Evaluation of Student Programs

Based on the results of observations, in-depth interviews and documentation studies regarding the evaluation of the student management program at Integrated Islamic Elementary School, it was carried out through an important process to ensure the effectiveness and efficiency of the programs that have been implemented. This evaluation can be carried out with various methods and objectives, such as evaluating program implementation, identifying deficiencies, and formulating necessary corrective actions. Evaluation of student programs at Integrated Islamic Elementary Schools includes: a) Program implementation: This evaluation aims to assess the extent to which student programs have been implemented in accordance with predetermined plans. Aspects that can be evaluated include activities that have been carried out, student participation, and support from related parties; b) Program quality: This evaluation aims to assess the extent to which student programs have achieved the stated objectives. Aspects that can be evaluated include the success of the program in improving the quality of education, developing student character, and empowering students. c) Student management: This evaluation aims to assess the effectiveness of student management in managing various aspects related to students. Aspects that can be evaluated include student planning, accepting new students, recording students in the main book, grouping students, and monitoring student progress. d) Student participation: This evaluation aims to assess the extent to which students are involved in student affairs programs. Aspects that can be evaluated include student participation in extracurricular activities, social activities, and other activities related to student self-development; e) Student satisfaction: This evaluation aims to assess the extent to which students feel satisfied with the student programs that have been implemented. Aspects that can be evaluated include student satisfaction with the activities that have been carried out, support provided by related parties, and the benefits obtained by students from the student program.

Evaluation of student programs at Integrated Islamic Elementary Schools can be carried out periodically, for example every semester or every year, to ensure that the programs that have been implemented can continue to be improved and provide maximum benefits for students. Indicators that can be used in evaluating student programs at Integrated Islamic Elementary School include 1) Program implementation: indicators that can be used to evaluate program implementation include activities that have been carried out, student participation, and support from related parties; 2) Program quality: indicators that can be used to evaluate program quality include the success of the program in improving the quality of education, developing student character, and empowering students; 3)

Student management: indicators that can be used to evaluate the effectiveness of student management include student planning, accepting new students, recording students in the main book, grouping students, and monitoring student progress, 4) Student participation: indicators that can be used to evaluate student participation in student programs include student participation in extracurricular activities, social activities, and other activities related to student self-development; 5) Student satisfaction: indicators that can be used to evaluate student satisfaction with student programs include student satisfaction with the activities that have been carried out, support provided by related parties, and the benefits obtained by students from the student program; 6) Coaching program: indicators that can be used to evaluate coaching programs include the Devotion to Almighty God coaching program, National Insight coaching program, Extracurricular coaching program, Student Leadership coaching program, Student Entrepreneurship coaching program, Talent and Ability coaching program, coaching program Physical Fitness and Artistic Power, Arts development program; 7) Improving school performance: indicators that can be used to evaluate improving school performance include developing an effective and efficient school organizational structure in accordance with needs, implementing school development in accordance with long-term, medium and short-term plans, towards achieving the school's vision and mission, and realizing significant improvements in school performance in accordance with the school's vision, mission and national education goals .

The results of student program evaluations can be used to improve the quality of student services in schools in the following ways, including formulating corrective actions. The results of student program evaluations can be used to identify deficiencies and formulate necessary corrective actions. For example, if the evaluation shows that student participation in extracurricular activities is still low, then the school can formulate corrective actions such as increasing promotion of extracurricular activities or adding a variety of extracurricular activities that attract students' interest. Improving program quality: The results of student program evaluations can be used to improve the quality of student programs that have been implemented. For example, if the evaluation shows that the student character development program has not been effective, then the school can improve the program by adding activities that are more varied and attract student interest.

Improving student management: The results of student program evaluations can be used to improve the effectiveness of student management in managing various aspects related to students. For example, if the evaluation shows that student management has not been effective in monitoring student progress, then the school can improve management by improving the system for recording and monitoring student progress.

Increasing student participation: The results of student program evaluations can be used to increase student participation in student programs. For example, if the evaluation shows that student participation in social activities is still low, then the school can increase student participation by holding social activities that are more interesting and beneficial for students. By using the results of student program evaluations, schools can make necessary improvements and upgrades to improve the quality of student services

provided. This can have a positive impact on student development and achievement in primary school.

V. CONCLUSION

The implementation of student management at the Majelis Tafsir Al-Quran Karawang Integrated Islamic Elementary School has been running through management activities with planning, implementation and evaluation stages carried out by the school principal and teachers. The results show that student programs can encourage and motivate students to develop the potential for initiative, creativity and courage to make decisions in the dimensions of the teaching and learning process in the school environment which has implications for increasing student learning achievement. However, there are still obstacles, namely school resource support which is not yet optimal for use and still needs improvement.

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